

Factors Influencing Crab Species Abundance in New England Seagrass Beds

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Abstract:

Crabs function as important predators and scavengers within the ecologically important seagrass habitat. Some crab species also have commercial and recreational importance. Seagrass beds are permanent habitat and nurseries for important fishery species. Changing crab population dynamics have the potential to affect the balance and health of seagrass bed environments of Nantucket. Here I set out to document the current abundance of crab within a Nantucket seagrass bed. How crab species diversity in Nantucket seagrass is effected by seagrass density and the seagrass proximity to a marsh is evaluated. Crab species have the potential to impact other crab species placement within the seagrass, therefore the relationships between crabs species found were evaluated. Four strands of baited crab pots were placed three times for twenty four hour soaks for ten weeks. Crab number and species were recorded. A seine net was used to capture species and sizes not captured by the baited pots. The study found five crab species *Libinia dubia*, *Carcinus maenas*, *Callinectes sapidus*, *Ovalipes ocellatus*. *C. maenas*, an invasive species, was found to be a significant percentage of the total crab population. The study found no evidence that marsh proximity or seagrass density affects crab diversity with all five species found at all locations. Increased crab population was found proximate to the marsh entrance. Effects of seagrass density were less distinct and varied by species. An avoidance relationship was found between *C. sapidus*, *C. maenas* and *L. dubia*. The most distinct negative relationship was between *C. sapidus* and *C. maenas* and *L. dubia*. Observation of pots containing *C. sapidus* showed evidence of inter and intra species predation. These finding suggest changes in seagrass density located near marshes and shifts in species, such as an increase in *C. Sapidus*, would have a significant impact on total crab population and dynamics.

Introduction:

Crabs play an important role as mid trophic consumers in the complex food web found within the ecologically important seagrass beds (2). Within this soft-sediment environment crabs are significant invertebrate predators of both soft bodied and shelled prey species (2, 11). Crabs are omnivorous scavengers consuming mollusks, fish, crustaceans, live plants, and other crabs (10, 13). Many crabs including *C. sapidus* (*Callinectes sapidus*,) are commercially and recreationally important to humans. Crab species are facing anthropological stresses including climate change, abiotic changes, introduction of invasive species, and declining seagrass habitat. Understanding the drivers of crab abundance in seagrass beds is helpful in efforts to predict crab response to stressors which will impact seagrass ecology.

Seagrass beds are critical shallow water habitats. There are species that use seagrass habitat throughout their lives or parts of their lives. Seagrass habitat are nurseries for invertebrates, fishes, birds and marine mammals. Many of these are important commercial and recreational fish, crustaceans and shellfish species. The seagrass itself aids in coastal protection, increasing water quality and carbon storage (1, 2,11). The seagrass beds have been stressed by anthropological activities. In the last forty years there has been a tenfold increase in reported loss of temperate seagrass beds worldwide. Eutrophication associated with sediment runoff, algae blooms, sea level rise and vegetation disturbance have all been identified as contributing factors to this loss (14). Declining health and loss of seagrass beds are a loss of crab habitat.

This experiment was performed on the Nantucket Harbor inland coastline which has a documented loss of seagrass. An aerial study by the Massachusetts Environmental Protection Agency in 2015 found an overall loss of 30% in twenty years. Seagrass declined from 1486.5 acres in 1995 to 1024.9 acres in 2015. The Nantucket harbor area which includes the study location experienced one of the largest eelgrass decline. Charles Costello, in summarizing the seagrass study findings on Nantucket by the EPA, noted that the areas with the largest seagrass loss correlated with the areas of greatest increased human population on the island and areas with increased runoff from upland. *Lyngbya* is a black invasive macro-algae found in areas of elevated nutrient levels associated with runoff and other pollution. It was found in some areas of the sea grass during the EPA study. *Lyngbya* can smother

seagrass ending its ability to serve as a nursery for fish and seed scallops both of these are food sources for crab species found in seagrass beds (3).

Another anthropological change with the potential to impact crab species is the introduction of non-native species of crab both by impacting sea grass health and through competition for resources. The introduction of twenty eight non-native species to seagrass worldwide is also thought to have contributed to seagrass decline with 64 percent having documented or likely negative effects (1, 15). Native species of crab found in southern New England waters include *O. ocellatus* (*Ovalipes ocellatus*), *C. sapidus* (*Callinectes sapidus*), *C. irroratus* (*Cancer irroratus*), *E. depressus* (*Eurypanopeus depressus*), *L. dubia* (*Libinia dubia*), *L. emarginata* (*Libinia emarginata*) and *P. acadianus* (*Pagurus acadianus*). There was also two invasive species, *C. maenas* (*Carcinus maenas*) and *H. sanguineus* (*Hemigrapsus sanguineus*) (10, 15). Many of these species inhabit seagrass beds. Investigations of eel grass beds in Cape Cod Bay in 1998 found the following crab species; *L. dubia*, *C. maenas*, and *C. irroratus* (10). *C. maenas* were found in significant numbers and was the second highest population at 798 individuals in K.L Heck et al experiment. Discussions with Yvonne Vaillancourt, the field director at the University of Massachusetts Nantucket Field Station and a literature search showed that information on current crab species diversity and abundance in Nantucket Harbor seagrass would benefit from updating. However, the presence of crab in this area is well known (Personal Conversation). During July 2016, a one-week collection in Folgers marsh and the edge of the seagrass beds adjacent to the marsh at the Nantucket Field station was made in a study of *The Effect of Abiotic Factors on Fish Diversity and Population of Mummichogs*. Minnow traps, baited with squid, captured several species of crab. Seine net captures and observations while snorkeling through a sea grass bed during that week showed a variety of crab species and size variation within species. This suggests that multiple crab species are present and impacting the biota of this seagrass bed.

Among the factors which may influence crab habitat selection are site location and seagrass density (10, 11). Jackson in *The Importance of Seagrass Beds as a habitat for Fishery Species* notes studies which suggest location of the seagrass bed in relation to the mouth of an estuary may influence species selection (11). In *A Global Crisis for Seagrass Ecosystems*, Robert J. Orth et al, states that closeness of seagrass to marsh habitats allows invertebrates use of both habitats (16). The area selected for this study contained both seagrass located at the mouth of the entrance to a salt march and sea grass more distant from it at the same depth to study this as a factor in crab abundance.

Along with proximity to other marine habitat, the density of seagrass has been studied as a contributing factor to abundance and species specific habitat selection. Seagrass can experience localized difference in density within the same seagrass meadow due to physical disturbances such as anchor damage, boat use and moorings (14, 16). Seagrass mirror most habitats in having an increased abundance of non-sessile organisms in areas of denser vegetation. However, *Decreasing Seagrass Density Negatively Influences Associated Fauna* by McCloskey et al., showed a preference by some species for low density seagrass which was noted to more closely resemble nearby sandy areas (14). Increased density of seagrass was found to increase hunting time. Populations of seed scallop have been found to be lower in the lower density areas of some seagrass meadows, suggesting more successful hunting within these more open areas (11,14, 16). McCloskey et al notes the possibility that competing species may prevent or remove a species from its preferred areas (14).

Native species may share or compete for seagrass beds with the invasive *C. maenas* and *H. sanguineus*. *C. maenas* was introduced to New England coastal waters around 1817 by boats releasing water from their ballasts. *H. sanguineus* (*Hemigrapsus sanguineus*) was more recently introduced to the east coast. It had invaded New Jersey in 1988 and by 1998 was found from Cape Hatteras to Cape Cod. (6,12,13). Although *H. sanguineus* has been found to prefer rocky tidal habitats they have also been found to forage over long distances. There is evidence that the *H. sanguineus* continues to expand its range. In James A. MacDonald et. al study, *The Invasive Green Crab and Japanese Shore Crab: behavioral interactions with a native crab species, the blue crab*, he proposes that *H. sanguineus* (*Hemigrapsus sanguineus*) may forage into areas typically occupied by *C. sapidus* (13). Laboratory studies have found that in direct food competition and aggressive episodes, juvenile *C. sapidus* are at a disadvantage to both *C. maenas* and *H. sanguineus* of similar size (13). *C. maenas* have also been found to be destructive to transplanted seagrass beds (5). Changing crab populations dynamics will have the potential to significantly impact the ecological balance and health of seagrass bed environments of Nantucket.

In *Biotic Resistance to Invasion: Native Predator Limits Abundance and Distribution of an Introduced Crab*, Catherine e. DeRivera et al. using both field and laboratory observation found that adult blue crab heavily preyed on green crab. Locations with high concentrations of *C. sapidus* were found to have fewer *C. maenas*. In their study *C. sapidus* presence were determined to be the most significant factor in decreasing *C. maenas*, compared to other possible variables (7). Cape Cod has been the northern most range of *C. sapidus*. However, recent studies suggest that the range is expanding north, into the Gulf of Maine associated with increased water temperatures (12). An expanded northern

range and increased water temperatures within Nantucket Harbor leads to the potential for increasing *C. sapidus* population within the study area. The likelihood of changing crab populations in seagrass beds and decline seagrass area makes increased understanding of the relationship between crab abundance and seagrass in New England important.

The objectives of this experiment included documenting the crab species abundance and temporal changes in the abundance through a ten week summer period within a Nantucket seagrass bed by documenting species and size of crab in 16 baited traps three times a week. The experiment investigates the effects of seagrass density and proximity to a marsh creek on crab abundance. The crab pots were placed on four strands with two strands placed at far and close locations to a salt marsh entrance. Two strands were placed in areas determined to be high density seagrass and two in low. Overall crab preference and preference by species regarding density and salt marsh proximity were observed. It examines the relationship between crab species within seagrass beds through field observation and analysis of crab avoidance. Hypotheses of this experiment are that the seagrass bed supports several crab species, with fluctuating populations through the summer period. That high density seagrass supports a larger population and diversity of crab. That proximity to a marsh creek supports a larger population and diversity of crab. An additional hypothesis is that there is a relationship between the crab species with the invasive green crab dominating the native crab species.

Methods

Study Site

The experiment took place on Nantucket Massachusetts, an island approximately 185 kilometers southeast of Boston. The experiment was performed in Nantucket harbor off the shore of the University of Massachusetts Boston Nantucket Field Station. The field station is situated on the north facing interior shoreline of Nantucket Harbor with Folgers Marsh next to it (Figure 1 & Figure 2). The experiment took place from June 5, 2017 to August 17, 2017.

Identifying Crabs Species and Temporal Changes:

To document the crab species present within the seagrass bed and temporal change in crab abundance at these locations. Sixteen baited traps divided between four strands were used to collect crab over a ten week period. The crab were sorted by species and size were measured. The first week of the 11-week period was used to identify the pot locations, test equipment and begin bait collection.

There were sixteen traps placed in the study location. The sixteen pots were divided into four strands of four pots each. Each strand was 30.48 meters long with a cinder block at one end to minimize drift. There was 7.6 meters between each pot. Each pot was located at the same water depth. The first strand's starting coordinates were 41 17' 45.89" north, 70 02' 39.86" west and ending at coordinates 41 17' 46.89" north, 70 02' 39.44" west. The second strand starting coordinates were at 41 17' 45.02" North, 70 02' 38.58" West, ending at 41 17' 45.78" North, 70 02' 39.44" West. The starting coordinates for strand three were 41 17' 46.38 North, 70 02' 31.76" West. The ending coordinates were 41 17' 48.13 North, 70 02' 28.72 west. Starting coordinates for strand four were 41 17' 46.38 North, 70 02' 31.76" West. The ending coordinates were 41 17' 48.13 North, 70 02' 28.72 west

For the initial three weeks, 50% of the sixteen traps were fishing bait net traps. Several of these traps were damaged in rougher water related with inclement weather conditions. As there was no significant difference in crab collection noted between the two trap types these eight were replaced with the Promar Collapsible Crab pots. From week four to week ten all traps were Promar collapsible crab pots.).

The Promar Collapsible Crab traps were baited with native fish collected in the area using the seine nets (Figure 2). The traps were baited Monday, Tuesday and Wednesday with silversides, eel and mummichugs collected in the area. The trap's bait bags were filled to one inch level. Crab species were documented Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday after 24 hour soaks. The captured crabs were sorted by species, counted and size measured using a twelve inch caliber. Crab were returned to the water a minimum of twenty feet from trap site. In addition seine nets were used to collect species that might not have been caught in the traps each Tuesday and Thursday for bait. Collection was made for ten weeks June 12, 2017 to August 17, 2017 to document temporal shifts in crab population. (Figure 4)

Impact of Lyngbya

During week three *Lyngbya* sp. was observed in the seagrass, this lead to an additional monitoring study of the lyngbya coverage from week four to week ten. A quadrat was used every Wednesday after the crab data collection was complete. The percent coverage of the Lyngbya was documented at each strand by percent coverage inside a square meter quadrat. The quadrat was placed by each of the cinder blocks to limit human disturbance (Figure 2 and Figure 14).

Effects of Seagrass Density and Proximity to a Salt Marsh

To assess the effect of proximity to a marsh and seagrass density on crab abundance the four strands of crab pots were placed in seagrass based on these conditions (Figure 2). Difference in crab species based on these two factors was assessed. In the initial placement of traps, strands one and two were placed close to the creek mouth entrance to Folgers Marsh. These strands were located in seagrass next to the sand bed where water flow from the creek was observed during ebb tide (Figure 2).

Strand placement was also divided between low and high density seagrass. Only *Zostera marina* was found in this seagrass meadow. For the experiment density was determined by percent coverage measured using a square meter quadrat. Greater than 50% coverage was considered high density, less than 50% was considered low density. Strands one and three were in high density seagrass with strands two and four at low density seagrass areas. The total number of crab at each strand and amount of each species was recorded (Figure 3). Each crab species was then analyzed for both marsh proximity and seagrass density preference. Temporal changes in each species distribution based on distance from marsh and seagrass density was then analyzed (Figure 5 through Figure 10).

Relationships between Crab Species.

To assess the relationship between species both evidence of interactions within the crab pot and statistical evidence of species avoidance were considered. The interactions between *L. dubia*, *C. maenas* and *C. sapidus* within each crab pot were noted. The evidence of predation and cannibalism in all pots were documented. The abundance of crab species at each location were analyzed to determine species avoidance within the different strand locations (Figures 11 through Figure 13).

Results

Identifying Crabs Species and Temporal Changes

Five species of crab were observed within the studied area: *L. dubia*, *C. maenas*, *C. sapidus*, *O. ocellatus* (*Ovalipes. Ocellatus*) and *D. sayi* (*Dyspanopeus Sayi*). In all four locations *L. dubia* was the most abundant species observed with a total population of 807(57.072%) over the ten weeks of data collection. This is followed by *C. maenas* with a total number of 377(26.662%). *C. sapidus* was the third most prevalent species, with 117(8.274%) observed. *D. sayi* and *O. ocellatus* were the least observed

crab in the pots with populations of 59 (4.173%) and 54 (3.819%) respectively. The invasive *H. sanguineus* were not observed in this experiment. There were other invertebrates captured in the pots including hermit crabs and horseshoe crabs (Figure 3).

Each species of crab demonstrated different temporal dynamics. *L. dubia* demonstrated a major increase in populations during weeks one and two of the experiment with an additional increase during week six. During weeks one and two a number of pregnant *L. dubia* were found in the pots at strands one and two (Figure 16). *C. maenas* showed a series of peaks and troughs throughout the ten weeks. *C. sapidus* population experienced an elevation in weeks two through six with the highest population occurring weeks three and four. *O. ocellatus* and *D. sayi* population were too small to determine any temporal changes (Figure 4 & 15). During the fifth week of observations an increase in boating, swimming and from shore fishing activities were noted in the area related to Independence Day celebrations potentially causing disruptions.

Impact of Lyngbya

Lyngbya was first observed on the seagrass during week three of the experiment. The highest percentage was observed during week four to week five. The greatest coverage occurred at strand two the low-density seagrass close to the marsh. Week six there was a decrease in the *lyngbya/hydrocoleum spp.* (Figure 14 and Figure 17). While *lyngbya* was present the water was observed to take a dark green to blackish tinge with decreased visibility (Figure 18). During weeks three through five, there was a decrease in *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* which then increased after week six. *C. sapidus* was undergoing a temporal population spike noted above in week four with the declining population from week four through week six (Figure 4 and Figure 15).

Effects of Seagrass Density and Proximity to a Salt Marsh

There was no difference in crab variety based on either seagrass density or proximity to a marsh entrance with all five species found at all four strands during the ten weeks. Locations close to the marsh had a larger crab population. There was no significant difference in total crab population based on seagrass density (Figure 3). However there were species preferences to both seagrass density and marsh proximity.

L. dubia demonstrated an overall preference for the location closer to Folgers marsh and for high-density seagrass. The preference for the locations close to Folgers marsh is strongly influenced by

the high population observed at this location in weeks one and two. Multiple egg bearing females were observed at this location during these weeks. *L. dubia* demonstrated a preference for high density seagrass through the ten week study (Figures 4 and 8). *C. maenas* population was consistently higher at strands one and two located close to the marsh entrance (Figure 2 and Figure 5). In the first three weeks *C. maenas* demonstrated no preference in seagrass density. From week four to week ten a greater population was observed in the low density seagrass (Figure 3 and Figure 6). However, this preference varied by location. . The observed *C. maenas* population at the close location favored the low density seagrass, while the smaller population at the far location, and was observed more frequently in the high density seagrass (Figure 3). *C. sapidus* demonstrated a preference for the locations distant from the marsh entrance at strands three and four, while there was no observed preference based on seagrass density (Figure 9 Figure 10). Density preferences and distance preferences for *O. ocellatus* could not be determined due to small observed populations.

Relationships between Crab Species

Observation of behavior and crab condition within the pots varied depending on species present. Bait was consumed in all pots. There was no observation of aggressive behavior between *L. dubia*, *C. maenas* and *O. ocellatus*. There was no predation or cannibalism noted in pots containing combinations of *L. dubia*, *C. maenas* or *O. ocellatus*. *C. sapidus* were observed with aggressive behavior within the pots. These crabs were observed clawing other blue crab and the other species found in the pots. When *C. sapidus* were present there was evidence of predation of *C. maenas* and *O. ocellatus*. There was evidence of cannibalism between *C. sapidus*. There was no evidence of predation of *L. dubia* observed. However, *L. dubia* with missing limbs were only seen in pots with *C. sapidus* also present. The *L. dubia* were observed consuming dead *C. maenas*, *C. sapidus* and *O. ocellatus* crab in these same pots. *C. sapidus* were observed with aggressive behavior towards each other, *C. maenas* and *O. ocellatus* within the pots during the crab counts. There was evidence of cannibalism of *C. sapidus*.

The relationship between the crab species were evaluated at each location to determine if the relationships were impacted by seagrass density or distance from Folgers marsh. *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* were found to have a negative relationship at the distant location from Folgers marsh. The negative relationship was less clear at the closer locations (Figure 13). *C. sapidus* demonstrated a negative relationship with both the green crab and the spider crab at all locations (Figures 11 and 12).

Discussion:

This study found no difference in crab species diversity either by location within the seagrass meadow or temporally with the same five species present throughout. There were significant changes in species population both by location and over time. This study identified five crab species present in the Nantucket seagrass from June 12, 2017 to August 17, 2017. The finding of *L. dubia* (57.072%), *C. maenas* (26.662%), *C. sapidus* (8.274%), *Dyspanopeus sayi* 4.173% and *O. ocellatus* (3.819%) may be compared with the results from *Fishes and Decapod Crustaceans of Cape Cod Eelgrass Meadows: Species Composition, Seasonal Abundance Patterns and Comparison with Unvegetated Substrates*, a two year study from 1955 to 1956 in Cape Cod eel grass beds by K.L Heck et al. The study used a significantly different collection method, using multiple trawling's for specimen collection. The three crab species found were *C. maenas* (38%), *Cancer irroratus* (5%) and *L. dubia*. (.01%) among the decapods collected (10).

C. maenas were present in significant numbers and make up a significant percentage of both study's population. In this study *C. maenas* was found in all four locations through the ten week, making up the second largest observed population at 26.662%. In K.L Heck et al, experiment, *C. maenas* made up 38 % of the decapod population and was the most abundant crab. These findings confirm the well-established *C. maenas* population in New England.

There was no *C. sapidus* collected in *Fishes and Decapod Crustaceans of Cape Cod Eelgrass Meadows: Species Composition, Seasonal Abundance Patterns and Comparison with Unvegetated Substrates* and K. L Heck et al notes the lack of warm water decapods collected. Their study took place up in Nauset Harbor, located north of Nantucket and thirty one years ago (10). In 2015, *The Savory Swimmer Swims North: A Northern Range Extension of the Blue Crab Callinectes Sapidus?* By David S Johnson, documented increased sightings of *C. sapidus* north of its historical range into the Gulf of Maine and Nova Scotia. He correlates this with increasing water temperatures in the area. He proposes that the range of *C. sapidus* will continue to expand into the Gulf of Maine (12). Northern movement of the *C. sapidus* range and rising water temperature in Nantucket suggests that *C. sapidus* populations in Nantucket Seagrass beds could be on the rise. It is hoped that this study's *C. sapidus* population findings will be useful for comparisons in future area population studies.

The temporal shift in crab populations varied by species. The largest number of *L. dubia* were observed during weeks one and two (Figure 4). *L. dubia* is known to demonstrate seasonal changes in

abundance in the Northeast with greater population found in the spring and autumn than in the summer (17). It is possible the elevation in week one and two, June 12th through June 22nd support this seasonal decrease. This population contained a number of egg bearing *L. dubia*. A longer term study further assesses its temporal patterns and its reproductive patterns in the area. This suggests a possible relationship between *L. dubia* reproduction and the temporal population change.

There were two unexpected occurrences which potentially impacted the crab distribution. One was the increase of human activity in the area during the week of Independence Day celebrations on the Island. Despite being a Sanctuary area and with marked research buoys there were several disturbances noted. These included increased boating and fishing in the area. The second was the bloom of lyngbya which was accompanied by a decrease observation of *L. dubia* and *C. maenas*. Lyngbya has been found on Nantucket since 2008 (8). Its presence was noted in locations other than the study site during the Eel Grass mapping in 2015 (3). Interestingly, there were a few observations of *L. dubia*, which are decorative crab, with lyngbya attached to its carapace. Although there was a decrease in both *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* populations during the lyngbya bloom, further study is needed of how lyngbya impact crab populations.

This study found that proximity to a salt marsh had a greater influence than seagrass density on crab population distribution. There was constantly a larger population of *C. maenas* at the locations close to the marsh throughout the ten weeks (Figure 5). While *L. dubia*'s overall preference was strongly influenced by a concentration of a population spike during weeks one and two at the close locations. The preference by *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* for proximity to a marsh opening is consistent with studies which demonstrate that the location of a seagrass bed next to an estuary has a positive impact on site selection (11). *C. maenas* live in both Marsh and seagrass beds. In *A Global Crisis for Seagrass Ecosystems*, R. J Orth, et al found that invertebrates in seagrass bed located near marsh habitat may use both locations. Based on R.J orth, et al findings the potential that *C. maenas* located at strand one and two are using both the seagrass bed and the marsh entrance could be investigated.

Although seagrass bed density had less influence on overall crab population, there were differences in species preference of seagrass density. *L. dubia* consistently favored high density seagrass (Figure 8). *C. maenas* preference varied within the study. *C. maenas* showed no preference for seagrass density in weeks one through three. After week four, observed *C. maenas* population at the close location favored the low density seagrass, while the smaller population at the far location, was observed more frequently in the high density seagrass (Figure 5 and Figure 6). As *C. maenas* foraging activities has

been shown to negatively influence newly planted seagrass beds (5). It is possible that seagrass density is influenced by *C.maenas* activities in established beds. Density at the study sites were not evaluated after the initial placement. It is possible that seagrass density at the sites changed during the experiment by crab activity or other influences such as the lyngbya which can negatively affect seagrass (8).

Relationships between Crab Species

An important influence on species abundance and individual species location within the seagrass habitat is crab species interaction. The analysis of crab species interactions were divided by strand to eliminate the potential that a concentration of elevated species population in an area would skew data results. It also allows for examination of species relationship at each location. There was a negative correlation between *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* at locations distant from the marsh at strands three and four. In the strands close to the marsh locations the population of both species were higher, with the negative correlation less distinct. There was no negative interaction noted within the pots as shown by evidence of predation and injury between *L. dubia*, *C. maenas* and *O. ocellatus* without the presence of *C. sapidus* (Figure 13).

C. sapidus had a negative correlation with both *L. dubia* and *C. maenas* (Figure 11 and Figure 12). The negative relationship between *C. sapidus* and *C. maenas* is well documented in the mid- Atlantic region. In this experiment there was a significant size difference between *C. sapidus* and *C. maenas*. *C. sapidus* carapace ranged from 2.54 cm to 16.637 cm with an average of 13.03cm. *C. maenas* average was 4.89cm with a range of 1.016 to 10.668 cm. *L. dubia* average was a 4.5 cm, with a range of 0.635 to 10.16 (Figure 19).

The observed aggressive *C. sapidus* behavior in the pots and evidence of predation on the other crab species along with cannibalism is consistent with the results found by Catherine DeRivera et al. In their study, *Biotic Resistance to Invasion: native Predator Limits Abundance and Distribution of an Introduced Crab* they found that adult *C. sapidus* preyed on *C. maenas* (7). These observations along with the potential increased *C. sapidus* point to *C. sapidus* having an increasing role in determining crab population. There is the potential for *C. sapidus* to play a significant role in controlling *C. maenas* populations as they do in the mid-Atlantic. Although, interactions between juvenile *C. sapidus* of similar size to *C. maenas* were not observed in this experiment. A study done in a laboratory setting showed that *C. maenas* out competed *C. sapidus* of similar size for food source and in aggressive episodes (13).

Consumption of young *C. sapidus* by *C. maenas* may also be impacting crab dynamics and could influence future interactions with shifting crab populations.

This study documents the current crab abundance within a Nantucket Seagrass bed. It documents that proximity to a marsh impacts crab population, while high seagrass density had less impact and varied by species. The crab interaction indicates that *C. sapidus* has a significant impact on other crabs within the seagrass beds.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. A map of Nantucket

Figure 2. Over view of experiment area. Field station right, Folgers marsh bottom middle, Marsh opening bottom left. Strand one, red (close high seagrass density), strand two. (Close, low seagrass density.), green, strand three (Far, high seagrass density) yellow and strand four (far, low seagrass density) pink. (left to right). Blue circles represent *Lyngbya* plots.

Figure 3. Distribution of crabs between the four strands. The crab community composition consisted of the observed number of crabs throughout the ten weeks in the pots of each strand

Figure 4. The temporal changes of four crab species found.

Figure 5. *C. maenas* (green crab) population distribution through the ten weeks by Distance from the Salt marsh.

Figure 6. *C. maenas* (green crab) population distribution based on seagrass density through the ten weeks.

Figure 7 *L. Dubia* (spider crab) population distribution based on distance from the salt marsh over the ten week period.

Figure 8 *L. dubia* (spider crab) population distribution based on seagrass density over the ten weeks.

Figure 9 *C. sapidus* (blue crab) population distribution based on distance from a salt marsh over the ten week period.

Figure 10 *C. sapidus* (blue crab) population distribution based on seagrass density over the ten week period.

Figure 11. Relationship between *L. dubia* (spider crab) and *C. sapidus* (blue crab) in each of the four strand locations.

Figure 12. Relationship between *C. sapidus* and *C. maenas* in each of the four strand locations.

Figure 13. Relationship between *L. dubia* (spider crab) and *C. maenas* (green crab) in each of the four strand locations.

Figure 14. *Lyngbya* coverage at each plot located by the cinder block of each strand.

Figure 15. Crab population change over 10 weeks.

Figure 16. Picture of Egg bearing *L. dubia*

Figure 17. Picture of *Lyngbya*

Figure 18. Area picture *Lyngbya*

Figure 19. Crab size average and Ranges

Figures.

Figure 1.

(Google Maps)

Figure 2

(Google Maps)

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10.

Figure 11

Avoidance between *L. dubia* and *C. sapidus*

Figure 12

Avoidance between Green and Blue crab

Figure 13

Avoidance between *L. dubia* and *C. maenas*.

Figure 14

Percent Coverage of Lyngbya

Week	Date	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Plot 4
3		Observed	Observed	Observed	Observed
4	7/05/2017	10%	25%	25%	20%
5	7/12/2017	10%	50%	30%	20%
6	7/19/2017	10%	15%	0%	0%
7	7/26/2017	0%	5%	0%	0%
8	8/02/2017	0%	0%	0%	0%
9	8/09/2017	0%	0%	0%	0%
10	8/16/2017	0%	10%	0%	0%

Figure 15

Figure 16.

Egg Bearing Female *L. dubia*.

Figure 17

Figure 18.

Figure 19.

Crab Carapace Average size and Range in Centimeters

Crab species	Average size (CM)	Smallest carapace length (Cm)	Largest carapace length (CM)
Blue crab	13.03	2.54	16.637
Green crab	4.89	1.016	10.688
Spider Crab	4.50	0.635	10.16

